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CONTAMINATION OF SOIL AROUND NON-FERROUS METALS SMELTER. LEAD AND CADMIUM

SKAŻENIE GLEB OŁOWIEM I KADMEM WOKÓŁ HUTY METALI NIEŻELAZNYCH

Summary: Emissions of dust containing heavy metals from processing and smelting was the reason of contamination of the surroundings of non-ferrous metals smelter by zinc, lead, cadmium, and other metals. Heavy metals cumulated in soil and bound to the humic matter could be the reason of its degradation.

Soil samples were taken along transects set with a compass in eight directions around non-ferrous metals smelter in Upper Silesia. The concentration of lead and cadmium was measured with conventional AAS method.

The highest content of Pb in soil was found in a distance of about 1500 m from the smelter and highest content of Cd was found 250 m from the metallurgical plant. It was probably due to grain-size composition of dust emitted by the smelter, local conditions of cumulation of heavy metals in the soil or the wind direction. The results indicated contamination of the soil environment by heavy metals in the vicinity of the smelter.

Key words: lead, cadmium, soil, non-ferrous metals smelter

During the last few decades plenty of the fields of human activities dramatically developed *e.g.* the industry. Industrialisation raised not only the progress of civilisation, but also caused some harms to the environment *e.g.* increase of the heavy metal content in soil and living organisms [1, 2]. The worse are changes in chemical properties of the soil around emitters of metallurgical dust.

In the forest soil some of heavy metals *e.g.* lead are accumulated in upper 20 cm [3, 4]. Sometimes the contamination of the soil by heavy metals could result in progressive degradation of the biotope [5].

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Heavy metals content in the soil is an important criterion of contamination of the environment.

The purpose of present study was to evaluate contamination of the upper layer of soil by lead and cadmium around a non-ferrous metals smelter in Upper Silesia (Southern Poland).

Material and methods

One of the major emitters of metals in the Upper Silesia industrial region area is zinc and lead smelting works "Miasteczko Śląskie". The plant started in 1968. Nowadays, it produces about 40% of zinc and 50% of lead smelted in Poland.

Samples of upper layer (0–5 cm) of the soil were collected in the distance of: 10 m, 25 m, 50 m, 100 m, 150 m, 200 m, 250 m, and further on in each 250 m up to 3000 m, in 8 directions: N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W and NW of the smelter.

Soil samples were air dried, passed through a sieve (1 mm mesh), and extracted with 0.1 M HCl [6]. After filtration, the concentration of lead and cadmium was measured by atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS).

Each soil sample was prepared in 3 replicates and the results are averaged. The quality of analytical procedures was controlled by using internal samples with known concentrations [7].

Obtained results were processed with SURFER for Windows.

Results and discussion

The natural concentration of Pb in soil is in the range of 25–40 $\mu\text{g/g}$ of soil [5]. In the soil of Upper Silesian industrial region the mean content of lead is about 50.9 $\mu\text{g/g}$ [8]. In the neighbourhood of non-ferrous smelter the lead content in soil was 443.9 $\mu\text{g/g}$ of soil, while the permissible limit is 100 $\mu\text{g/g}$. The most polluted area was in radius of 250 m from the emission source. Most of contaminants were deposited West of the plant and heavy loads of Pb were found NE of the plant. This is because the dust from lead and zinc smelting process is driven there with winds (Fig. 1).

In Poland the concentration of Cd in soil is in the range of 0.01–49.7 $\mu\text{g/g}$ [5, 9]. Its main sources are dust emitted from non-ferrous metals smelters [8].

In the investigated area the Cd content in upper layer of the soil was in the range of 0.4–178.7 $\mu\text{g/g}$. The average concentration of Cd was 13.1 $\mu\text{g/g}$, when the upper limit in farmland soil is 3–5 $\mu\text{g/g}$ [5].

The most contaminated was the area in directions: W and NE from the plant (Fig. 2), and the heaviest loads of Cd were in the radius 25–750 m from the plant. This could be because of granulometric composition of the emitted dust.

In the soil of old dumping place of wastes from zinc oxide plant (nowadays closed), situated in the direction W of the smelter the Pb content reached 6510.7 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in the distance 1000 m in the direction W of the plant, and Cd – 395.1 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in the distance 750 m in the direction W of the plant. The correlation coefficient between Cd or Pb content in soil, and the distance from the emission source was statistically important ($p > 0.05$).

Fig. 1. Distribution of lead in upper layer of soil in the surroundings of the zinc and lead smelter (Upper Silesia)

Fig. 2. Distribution of cadmium in upper layer of soil in the surroundings of the zinc and lead smelter (Upper Silesia)

Conclusions

1. The most contaminated by lead and cadmium was the soil in 1000 m radius from the smelter.
2. The highest content of metals in soil was in the direction W and NE of the plant. The area West of the plant was contaminated by wastes from zinc oxide plant, which were dumped there some time ago. The pollution of the NE area is because of the metalliferous dust that is driven there with winds, which are in Poland mainly from SW direction.

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SKAŻENIE GLEB OŁOWIEM I KADMEM WOKÓŁ HUTY METALI NIEŻELAZNYCH

Streszczenie

Trwająca od 1968 roku emisja zanieczyszczeń, zawierających m.in. metale ciężkie, doprowadziła do znacznego skażenia wierzchniej warstwy gleb ołowiem i kadmem w sąsiedztwie Huty Cynku „Miasteczko Śląskie”.

Z terenów przyległych do huty metali nieżelaznych pobierano próbki gleb z głębokości od 0 do 5 cm, wzdłuż transektów w ośmiu kierunkach świata (N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W i NW), odpowiednio w odległości 10, 25, 50, 100, 150, 200, 250 m i dalej aż do 3000 m.

Zawartość Pb i Cd oznaczono metodą absorpcji atomowej (AAS).

Maksymalną zawartość Pb stwierdzono w odległości 1500 m od emitora, Cd natomiast w odległości 250 m. Największą kumulację omawianych metali odnotowano w kierunku W, gdzie wcześniej istniało składowisko odpadów zakładu tlenku cynku. Również znacznie obciążony jest kierunek NW, co związane jest z cyrkulacją powietrza na terenie Polski (z kierunku SW) i składem granulometrycznym opadających pyłów, a także lokalnymi warunkami, które sprzyjają kumulacji metali ciężkich (typ gleby, zawartość substancji organicznej itp.).

Zawartość Pb i Cd jest dodatnio skorelowana z odległością od źródła emisji ($p > 0,05$).

Najbardziej skażonym Pb i Cd obszarem, przyległym do huty metali nieżelaznych, jest strefa 1000 m wokół emitora.

Słowa kluczowe: ołów, kadm, gleba, huta metali nieżelaznych

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